

Photocatalysed Oxidation of Glyoxal by Dioxygen

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Photoinitiated oxidation of glyoxal by dioxygen was studied in the presence of several catalysts (Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Mn^{VII}, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} acetylacetonate) and various sensitizers (methylene blue, tetrasulphophthalocyanine, Fe^{III} tetrasulphophthalocyanine, Co^{II}, eosine, anthraquinone-2-sulphonate). Fe^{III} was found to be the most effective catalyst. The mechanism for Fe^{III} catalysis has been deduced. None of the sensitizers accelerate the reaction.

The oxidation of glyoxal by O₂ photocatalysed by Fe^{III} yields CO₂ as the only product. ϕ_r of the reaction is 1.174 and the rate constant $3.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Glyoxal (OHC-CHO) belongs to low molecular weight organic substances occurring in natural surface waters. It can get into surface waters by several ways: (i) from the atmosphere¹: glyoxal was shown to be formed in the atmosphere in ring-opening photooxidative reactions of phenolic compounds^{2,3} and deposited from the atmosphere into surface waters environment^{2,4}; (ii) by its formation in situ: in reactions of water humic acid components⁵ or as an intermediate in the transformation of microorganisms excretion products; and (iii) as a result of human industrial activities, e.g. manufacturing of glyoxylic acid from glyoxal^{6,7}. The diurnal fluctuations of several low molecular weight organic compounds, including glyoxal, in seawater were investigated by Mopper and Stahovec⁸.

Since glyoxal was reported to have a significant mutagenic activity^{8,9}, it is a matter of considerable interest to explore the possible pathways of its decomposition and transformation in water ecosystems. For drinking water treatment, the oxidation through the ozone-H₂O₂ combination was recommended¹⁰. The ozonation of glyoxal was studied by Caprio *et al.*¹¹ and their results indicate that not only O₃ itself but also molecular oxygen take part in the reaction process which proceed through a radical mechanism.

Glyoxal was shown to undergo photochemical oxidation by dioxygen in the presence of catalytic amounts of ferric ions¹²⁻¹⁴.

The present study is focused on photoinitiated reaction of glyoxal with dioxygen, the catalytic influence of metal ions and the sensitizing influence of various sensitizers, with the goal to elucidate the mechanistic principles of the reaction.

Results and Discussion

Thermal (dark) reaction of glyoxal with dioxygen does not proceed, not even in the presence of cata-

lyst (Table 1). Since glyoxal does not absorb radiation with wavelengths above 250 nm (Fig. 1a), it can be expected—and was verified in a blank experiment—that direct photoinitiated reaction with O₂ does not occur (to a measurable extent). Upon addition of Fe^{III}, a glyoxal-Fe^{III} complex absorbing radiation in photodynamic region (290–400 nm) is formed (Fig. 1). In Fig. 2, the dependences of O₂ consumption rates (as O₂ volume consumed in 90 min of reaction) on glyoxal and Fe^{III} concentrations are demonstrated: both dependences show a distinct saturation effect. Fe^{III} added as Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate has a positive effect on the glyoxal reaction with O₂ as well (Table 1), though no interaction with glyoxal can be observed in the absorption spectrum. Other metal ions (Mn^{VII}, Mn^{II} and Cu^{II}) were found inefficient as catalysts for the reaction.

The effect of sensitizers on the reaction glyoxal + O₂ is summarised in the second part of Table 1. No sensitizer was found to affect positively the oxidation of glyoxal by dioxygen. Combinations of the catalyst (Fe^{III}) and various sensitizers do not increase the rate observed in the catalytic reaction; two sensitizers eosine and anthraquinone-2-sulphonate, however, slow down the reaction rate of the catalysed reaction which is an unusual phenomenon.

The positive action of Fe^{III} in photoinitiated oxidation of glyoxal by O₂ may be interpreted in the following two ways. (i) The absorbing complex glyoxal-Fe^{III} is excited (supposedly to T₁ state),

the excited complex reacts directly with dioxygen,

this reaction is spin-allowed in variance to the reaction of a substrate in ground singlet state. (ii) The absorbing complex glyoxal-Fe^{III} is excited with the excitation followed by an intramolecular

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (a) glyoxal, and (b) glyoxal-Fe^{III} complex; glyoxal 0.04 mol dm⁻³, Fe^{III} 1.6 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, pH=3.5.

Fig. 2. Dependences of O₂ consumption after 90 min of irradiation on initial substrate and ferric ions concentrations, respectively (A) Fe^{III} 1.6 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, pH=3.0; (B) glyoxal 0.04 mol dm⁻³, pH=3.0.

TABLE 1—REACTION OF GLYOXAL WITH DIOXYGEN UNDER VARIOUS CONDITIONS

Reaction	Catalyst/ Sensitiser*	O ₂ consumption after 90 min of irradiation ml
Thermal	No catalyst	0
	Fe ^{III}	0
Photo	No catalyst	0.9
	Catalysed by:	
	Mn ^{II}	3.0
	Mn ^{VII}	2.7
	Cu ^{II}	0.6
	Fe ^{III}	15.3
	Fe ^{III} -acetylacetonate	10.4
	Fe ^{III} -acetylacetonate + Fe ^{III}	16.9
	Sensitised by:	
	Methylene blue	0.8
	Methylene blue + Fe ^{III}	16.3
	TSP Co ^{II}	1.2
	TSP Co ^{II} + Fe ^{III}	16.9
	TSP Fe ^{III}	2.3
	TSP Fe ^{III} + Fe ^{III}	16.3
	Eosine	0.2
	Eosine + Fe ^{III}	8.6
	AQS	0.8
	AQS + Fe ^{III}	4.4

*TSP=Tetrasulphophthalocyanine; AQS=Anthraquinone-sulphonate.

ligand-metal electron transfer; the electron transfer results in photoreduction of Fe^{III} to Fe^{II},

The complex of Fe^{II} (or liberated Fe^{II} ions themselves) catalyses the subsequent thermal reaction of the substrate with dioxygen—this reaction mecha-

nism with photochemical formation of the active form of catalyst followed by thermal (nonphotochemical) reaction of a substrate is called photocatalysis¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

In the first case (i), the reaction proceeds only under irradiation and stops as soon as irradiation is terminated because of the short-living triplet states. In the second case (ii), the reaction may proceed for some time after termination of irradiation (post-irradiation effect) until the photochemically generated catalyst is deactivated. The post-irradiation effect in the system studied is shown in Fig. 3. The reaction was followed intermittently in the light and in the dark, and O₂ consumption was measured throughout the light as well as dark periods. The reaction continues in the dark periods and apparently, the reaction rate of the dark reaction increases with repeated irradiation, i.e. with the accumulation of catalyst.

Fig. 3. Post-irradiation effect; glyoxal 0.04 mol dm⁻³, Fe^{III} 1.6 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, pH=3.5; L=irradiated (light) periods and (D)=dark periods.

Since photochemically generated Fe^{II} is the supposed catalyst, the concentration of Fe^{II} in the reaction mixture was determined for various times of irradiation, both under N₂ and in O₂ saturated solutions, and correlated with the kinetic curves. The results are demonstrated in Fig. 4. The photoreduction of Fe^{III} to Fe^{II} under N₂ is very fast—the reduction of 80% Fe^{III} added is completed within 5 min; in O₂ saturated solution, a constant ratio between Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} is reached after 25 min of irradiation, with 33% of the total Fe present as Fe^{II}. The ratio Fe^{II} : Fe^{III} depends on the relation between the rates of catalyst formation and deactivation, i.e. the rate of precursor photoreduction to catalyst and rate of catalyst reoxidation by O₂.¹⁸

The inhibition of the catalysed reaction by the sensitizers anthraquinone-2-sulphonate and eosine, was expected to be caused by preventing the photoreduction of Fe^{III}. Anthraquinone-2-sulphonate, however, accelerates photoreduction of Fe^{III} in the reaction system—the concentration of Fe^{II} in O₂

Fig. 4. Photoreduction of Fe^{III} (●) in O₂ saturated solution and (○) under N₂; glyoxal 0.04 mol dm⁻³, Fe^{III} 1.6 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³.

saturated solution reaches 75% of the total Fe after 10 min of irradiation. Since neither inner filtration of radiation nor complexation of metal ions by a sensitizer molecule takes part in the systems, an explanation of the inhibiting action of the sensitizers will need further investigation.

Though Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate has significant absorption in the photodynamic region, its action in the reaction of glyoxal with dioxygen is not sensitizing but exclusively photocatalytic. As demonstrated in Fig. 5: (i) the reaction shows a long (15 min) induction period, (ii) the post-irradiation effect of

Fig. 5. Photoinitiated reaction of glyoxal with O₂: (●) without catalyst, (●) with 4 × 10⁻⁴ M Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate, and (○) with 1.6 × 10⁻⁴ M FeCl₃; glyoxal 0.04 mol dm⁻³.

the reaction is significant and (iii) after approximately 60 min of irradiation, the reaction rate reaches the value of maximum reaction rate of the system glyoxal + Fe^{III}.

Glyoxal and Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate do not form a mixed-ligand complex, the absorption of the system in the first stages of the reaction is therefore due to Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate exclusively. During irradiation period, Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate is gradually decomposed with possible photoreduction of Fe^{III} to Fe^{II} due to an electron transfer from the ligand moiety of Liberated Fe^{III} (resp. Fe^I) may form complexes with glyoxal. The glyoxal-Fe^{III} complex is photochemically reduced to glyoxal-Fe^{II} complex (as in the system where FeCl₃ was added). The time necessary for Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate decomposition and active catalyst (glyoxal-Fe^{II}) formation is the cause of the long induction period of the reaction. After decomposition of all Fe^{III}-acetylacetonate, the available Fe^{III} concentration reaches that of the glyoxal+FeCl₃ system; hence the reaction rate may reach (and actually reaches) the value $\nu_{\max}$ of the latter system. The post-irradiation effect in the reaction represents the proof for the photocatalytic mechanism.

Quantum yield of the reaction glyoxal + O₂ catalysed by Fe^{III}, ϕ_r is 1.174. The value of ϕ_r is relatively high but not high enough to be, besides the post-irradiation effect, another proof for photocatalytic mechanism; for the purpose ϕ_r one order of magnitude higher should be required.

The reaction of glyoxal with dioxygen catalysed by photochemically formed Fe^{II} proceeds to 100% conversion with stoichiometry substrate : O₂ = 1 : 1 (Fig. 6). No organic product is formed by the reaction, the only product being carbon dioxide.

The reaction rate constant (k) of the pseudomolecular reaction with respect to glyoxal is $3.30 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ up to the concentration of the substrate $0.017 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Oxidation of glyoxal by dioxygen requires a catalyst to proceed. In the presence of Fe^{III} the reaction proceeds by photocatalytic mechanism with Fe^{II} being the photocatalyst. The following equations may describe the mechanism of glyoxal oxidation by O₂ :

Catalyst formation :

Substrate (glyoxal) oxidation :

Catalyst deactivation (reoxidation) :

The transition metal ions tested for the catalytic activity in the reaction glyoxal + O₂ included two metal ions most abundantly occurring in natural waters : iron and manganese. Manganese has been found to be an ineffective catalyst for the reaction, and iron, on the other hand, has been proven to enable—via its photocatalytic action—the oxidative transformation of glyoxal by dioxygen. Since similar results have been found in our previous works^{13,14,18} for other aliphatic compounds related to natural waters and since the crucial experimental conditions of our laboratory experiments (wavelength range emitted by the source, O₂ and catalyst concentrations, temperature) have been adjusted to correspond to the fresh water reality, the photocatalytic mechanism seems to be a common principle in photoinitiated dioxygen oxidations of polar aliphatic organic substances in natural waters.

Fig. 6 O₂ consumption curves and respective limits of O₂ consumption for 100% conversion (for 1 : 1 substrate : O₂ stoichiometry) : (○) 0.008 M glyoxal + 1.6×10^{-4} M FeCl₃, (●) 0.017 M glyoxal + 1.6×10^{-4} M FeCl₃, and (○) 0.04 M glyoxal + 1.6×10^{-4} M FeCl₃.

Experimental

Glyoxal monomer, $C_2H_2O_2$, 40% solution (Aldrich) or trimer, $3C_2H_2O_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (Merck) were used as such. Fresh solutions of glyoxal were prepared.

$FeCl_3$ and $MnCl_2$ (Lachema, Czechoslovakia) were dissolved in 0.1M HCl; Fe^{III} -acetylacetonate (Merck) was dissolved in a small portion of acetone and diluted with water. $KMnO_4$ and $CuCl_2$ (Lachema, Czechoslovakia) were dissolved in water.

Stock solutions of sensitizers: methylene blue (Lachema, Czechoslovakia), eosine (Lachema, Czechoslovakia), anthraquinone-2-sulphonate Na salt (Merck), tetrasulphophthalocyanine- Co^{II} and tetrasulphophthalocyanine- Fe^{III} (prepared according to Weber and Busch¹⁹) were prepared by dissolution in water. All stock solutions as well as all reaction mixtures were handled with careful minimisation of daylight exposure.

For all solutions double-distilled water was used, with second distillation carried out with $KMnO_4$ and NaOH.

Fe^{II} ions were determined spectrophotometrically using 1,10-phenanthroline ($\lambda_{max}=510$ nm, $\epsilon_{510}=1.1 \times 10^4$ mol⁻¹ dm cm⁻¹). Absorption spectra were measured on a Beckman DB-G spectrophotometer.

The amount of total organic residue present in the reaction mixture was determined by the dichromate semi-micro method²⁰.

Irradiation procedure: A substrate solution (20 ml) was vigorously shaken with oxygen in a thermostated quartz vessel and irradiated with a TESLA RVK 400 medium pressure Hg lamp (400 W); intense emission lines lay in the regions 290–365 and 435–580 nm. The amount of oxygen consumed was measured volumetrically by a gas burette, the accuracy being ± 0.02 ml O_2 and the reproducibility better than 3%. Carbon dioxide was absorbed in the upper part of the reaction vessel by KOH. O_2 consumptions were followed for 90 min.

Determination of quantum yield (ϕ_r): The radiation was monochromatised by a UV KSIF 313 metal interference filter (Carl Zeiss Jena, East Germany); the filter transmits lines with wavelength of 297, 303 and 313 nm. The light flux incident upon the

reaction vessel was determined by ferrioxalate actinometry²¹. Since the geometry in the radiation intensity measurement was the same as in measuring the rate of O_2 consumption, and since the light flux did not change with time, it was assumed that the light flux incident upon the reaction cell in the photochemical reaction was the same as that of the actinometric experiment.

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